

AI Regulation and the Technical Language of Speech Synthesis

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Abstract

Speech synthesis has garnered increasing interest with global efforts to regulate artificial intelligence (AI), including deepfakes. Policymakers must draft careful wording to prevent societal harm and identify responsible parties. Legal AI provisions must be accurate, especially when instructing responsible parties to act, as seen in the transparency obligations across current AI regulations worldwide. But AI and generative AI are broad terms, and analogies from image and video domains do not translate well to speech. Current AI policy focussing on speech synthesis *outputs* overlooks portable *models* and complex *workflows* wherein speaker embeddings that encode voice identity can be developed independently and later repurposed. This paper traces the convergence of text-to-speech, voice conversion, speaker verification, and speech recognition, highlighting where legal definitions may fail to capture the technical components that enable voice cloning.

Index Terms: AI regulation, speech synthesis, deepfakes, voice cloning, voice conversion, text-to-speech

1. Introduction

The promise of speech synthesis has held the heartbeat of artificial intelligence (AI) since around the time of AI's claimed inception at the 1956 Dartmouth Summer Research Project on Artificial Intelligence, where a key objective was to "find how to make a machine use language" [1]. Modern speech synthesis has longstanding scientific foundations with the first digital synthesis emerging from Bell Labs in 1962 [2]. The scientific terms often used in modern contexts to discuss so-called *AI speech* [3] in the 21st century can have specific technical meanings. This paper addresses several key terms wherein the technical meanings have shifted alongside developments in the field of speech synthesis, focussing specifically on the pitfalls of applying certain terms to speech synthesis policy and regulation.

AI-anything is considered a global hot topic across sectors, and the AI prefix is now being defined legally. Various references to synthetic audio, voice, and "deepfake" have found their way into codified law in Singapore [4], South Korea [5, 6], California [7], Tennessee [8], and Australia [9] and regulations in China [10], Brazil [11], and the European Union (EU) [12]. All of these jurisdictions have some form of transparency obligation wherein audiences must know whether they are hearing a human. Transparency obligations include labelling, watermarking, and notifications to individuals whose voice is represented. Emerging laws and regulations assign transparency obligations to different parties in different ways, and the nature of responsibility requires an understanding of technical concepts beyond simple interpretations of inputs and outputs.

Prior attempts have been made to clarify speech deep-

Figure 1: *Speaker embeddings can be used as general-purpose identity models in text-to-speech (TTS), voice conversion (VC), automatic speaker recognition (ASR), and automatic speaker verification (ASV) systems. Legal AI systems (red dash) do not account for portable models that encode speaker identity.*

fake terminology for non-experts [13], but do not foreground the regulatory significance of speaker embeddings as portable models that can be easily repurposed across systems, workflows, and tasks (demonstrated in Figure 1). Because speaker embedding models are portable and multifunctional, ensuring transparency of chain-of-custody with these models in speech synthesis is difficult for AI policy. Recent work from legal scholars has challenged regulatory language on deepfakes for unclear definitions and insufficient transparency obligations [14, 15], but fails to address speech synthesis explicitly. A growing number of stakeholders have critiqued AI transparency obligations for speech synthesis in non peer-reviewed technical reports¹, industry blog posts², and policy papers³. However, at the time of this writing there are no known peer-reviewed articles that question transparency obligations for speech synthesis or speech deepfakes at the level of voice *models* in the context of synthesis *workflows*.

2. Framing speech synthesis as AI

While AI policies treat speech synthesis as a form of AI, this was not always the case. Underpinning mathematical formulations of speech technology were widely regarded as problems for telecommunications and engineering through the 1970s and 1980s [16, 17, 18], and this allowed speech

¹<https://foundation.mozilla.org/en/research/library/in-transparency-we-trust/research-report>

²<https://www.pindrop.com/article/does-wat-ermarking-protect-against-deepfake-attacks>

³<https://www2.datainnovation.org/2024-ai-watermarking.pdf>

synthesis to develop independently from the budding new field of AI. Very few (if any) speech synthesis articles were published in prominent AI conferences of the time⁴ because the intellectual thread of AI was symbolic reasoning, whereas speech synthesis necessarily requires acoustic signal processing. Only since DeepMind’s WaveNet [19] in 2016 has speech synthesis been re-framed as AI, now falling under the umbrella of generative AI – a term that has subsequently entered into legal vocabularies.

2.1. Converging subdisciplines

Before “AI voice deepfakes” there were speech synthesis models. The evolution of speech synthesis technology occurred at the same time as automatic speaker verification (ASV) and automatic speech recognition (ASR), with these subdisciplines often sharing similar types of statistical models [20, 21, 22]. The intersection between ASR and speech synthesis came in 1962 from *analysis-by-synthesis* wherein speech could be understood by how it is generated [23]. The concept of analysis-by-synthesis forms the basis of modern speech synthesis encoder-decoder workflows (discussed in Section 4). The intersection between speech synthesis spoofing and ASV came in 2001, when an ASV system was made “robust to imposture using synthetic speech” [24]. Therefore, synthetic speech spoofs predate the deep learning revolution, and the popularisation of the term “AI deepfake”, by more than a decade.

As speech synthesis, ASV, and ASR continued to converge, they also informed each other. Their interplay extends beyond generative adversarial networks (GANs) that were popularised in early AI policy discourse [25]. For example, techniques from ASR can be used downstream to evaluate the quality of synthetic speech [26], saving costs from human evaluation at scale. Rigorous scientific methods from ASV evaluation have become standard for evaluating target speaker adaptation of speech synthesis, and calculating similarity scores between speaker embeddings. When integrated directly into speech synthesis workflows, ASV has been used for multi-speaker adaptation in text-to-speech (TTS) synthesis [27]. Further for voice conversion (VC) synthesis, ASR has provided phonetic labels in unit-selection workflows [28] and ASR acoustic models have been used in many-to-one conversion [29].

2.2. Language gaps for AI transparency

Terminology for speech synthesis is becoming unstable with precise scientific terms now gravitating toward “deepfake” as a label that dominates global AI policy discourse. Terms such as “AI-generated” and “AI-manipulated” are relied on within the image and video domains [30] and repeated in various formulations of AI regulation [5, 7, 9, 10, 12]. A generated versus manipulated dichotomy can be misleading for the speech domain due to the historical labelling and evaluation of TTS and VC datasets. These two types of speech synthesis have also shown differential performance in how the synthetic speech is detected [31, 32, 33]. However, both TTS and VC are by definition generated as synthetic, even when changes to style, content, or identity are performed through disentanglement [34, 35].

Global AI policy perspectives towards speech synthesis resonate that transparency is important, with some jurisdictions aiming to establish comprehensive labelling frameworks focussed on the output of speech synthesis systems [36]. However, many terms are used inconsistently

across policies in addition to being confused with technical scientific language. In the EU AI Act, an “AI system” is regulated differently from an “AI model”. The latter is not well-defined, but described as general-purpose, self-supervised, and having at least a billion parameters [12]. Such legalistic language risks missing the technical nuances that arise when discussing speech or speaker *embeddings* used as *models* wherein speech and speaker representations can be integrated into *workflows* [37].

Current policy frameworks remain focused on human perception through disclosure obligations regarding the output of speech synthesis systems [7, 10, 12]. Transparency obligations that focus solely on synthetic outputs may overlook the role of these models, whose lifecycle (creation, storage, transfer, and reuse) may require explicit consideration in regulation design. Speech models that encode voice characteristics can persist independently of the systems that produce them, and can be repurposed for speech deepfake creation. The following sections illustrate this gap for speech synthesis models (Section 3) and workflows (Section 4), highlighting implications for AI policy.

3. Speech synthesis models

What is meant by *model* in speech research differs from legal usage of *AI-model*. In speech research, a model is an architecture or framework trained on data to emulate a function. Models can generate intermediary representations, interface with other models, and compose into larger systems [27, 37, 38]. However, in law and policy AI-models [12] can mean nearly the opposite, referring to an elaborate construct that stands alone, performs general-purpose tasks at scale, and produces user-facing outputs. Introducing additional terms such as AI-systems [7, 12] and AI-services [10] further obfuscates what, exactly, is being regulated in speech synthesis. What legal language misses is that speech deepfakes can involve many models both internal and external to a system, and therefore many intermediary representations. The representations themselves can stand alone or be recomposed into other models or systems. The substantive matter is that models distilling speaker identity from labelled data remain unclear candidates for AI regulation.

3.1. Speech synthesis models through the years

From a historical perspective, a model for speech synthesis has held many meanings, including early efforts to describe or explain how human speech works. Early modelling of vowel spectra from 3D vocal tract measurements [48] was precursory to the source-filter model of speech production [49]. Mathematical models of anatomy described co-articulation of vowels and consonants in terms of vocal tract shapes [50]. In the early days of digital computerised speech synthesis, a common theme was to first model apparent human capability as a means to simulate it with computer programming [51]. Scientists were using speech synthesis models to simultaneously discover the fundamental mechanisms of *what speech is, how humans produce it, and how machines synthesise it* [52].

Generative models for speech synthesis included theories of sound structure motivated by various linguistic theories of the 1960s [53]. The first digital TTS synthesis system originated in Tokyo in the late 1960s [54]. That system was capable of aligning breath groups with syntactic structure and adding stress on phonemes. The channel vocoder [55] enabled significant speech compression

⁴*IJCAI (1969), AAAI (1980), ICML (1980), NeurIPS (1987)*

Table 1: *Embedding types used in speech synthesis pipelines. ASV = automatic speaker verification; ASR = automatic speech recognition; SSL = self-supervised learning; VC = voice conversion; TTS = text-to-speech. External: trained independently of downstream synthesis task. Repurposable: can be transferred across tasks. Speaker ID: encodes speaker identity.*

Type	Embedding	Original Task	External	Repurposable	Speaker ID
Speaker	i-vector [39]	ASV	✓	✓	✓
	d-vector [40]	ASV	✓	✓	✓
	x-vector [41]	ASV	✓	✓	✓
	ECAPA-TDNN [42]	ASV	✓	✓	✓
	GE2E [43]	ASV	✓	✓	✓
	WavLM [44]	SSL (multi-task)	✓	✓	✓
Content	PPG [29]	VC	✓	✓	–
	wav2vec 2.0 [45]	ASR	✓	✓	–
	HuBERT [46]	SSL for ASR	✓	✓	–
Style	Global Style Tokens [47]	TTS	–	~	–
	Tacotron Embeddings. [27]	TTS	–	~	✓

for early telecommunications. The phase vocoder [56] later introduced the ability to modify pitch and duration independently, opening the door for applications benefiting those with sight or hearing impairments. Concurrently, formant synthesizers emerged as a practical alternative to articulatory models, offering greater controllability with lower computational demands [57] and finding applications in both psychological speech perception studies and early text-to-speech systems.

Parametric models based on analysis-synthesis techniques allowed speech synthesis to computationally scale to larger and more diverse speech datasets [58]. Finding ways for speech waveforms to be represented through parameters set the stage for statistical learning models of the early 2000s [38]. Generative models could learn appropriate speech parameters from training data [22, 59] and eventually incorporate elements of controllability for voice characteristics through speaker adaptation [60].

3.2. Speech synthesis neural embedding models

There are many types of neural embedding models to represent distilled information from speech including about speaker identity, spoken content, and style or prosody. Table 1 summarises well-known embedding types that can be constructed for an original task (e.g., ASV) and later applied to other speech synthesis pipelines. Some of these embeddings are developed entirely external to downstream tasks, while others may learn to model information simultaneously during training of a speech synthesis system. Many of these models originated from the subfield of ASV and were later explored in speech synthesis for controllability [27, 47] and to adapt to very large speech datasets where variation among speakers proved challenging [61]. Further refinements resulted from disentanglement research, which aims to decouple information either to purify speaker embeddings [34] or to factor speech into separate representations for content, timbre, pitch, and rhythm [26, 62, 63].

3.3. Reflections on models in AI policy

One of the clearest challenges for AI policy concerning neural embedding models described in Section 3.2 is that the models themselves do not produce audio output unless they are integrated into a speech synthesis workflow. Furthermore, embeddings that model speaker identity occupy a legal grey area in privacy laws concerning biometric data [64]. They are not uniquely identifying on their own, cannot be inverted to reconstruct the input voice sample that they were derived from, and a disentangled embedding for content or style does not necessarily identify a

speaker. Yet speaker embeddings nonetheless encode characteristics for identification, regardless of the downstream task. Speaker models pose particular challenges for AI policy transparency due to difficulty tracing their provenance as modular components in speech synthesis workflows.

4. Modern speech synthesis workflows

Policymakers stand to benefit from understanding that multiple speech synthesis workflows exist. A workflow captures the full scope of speech synthesis from input to output, where the input type and intermediary steps can vary widely. Workflows may be composed of distinct modular systems (as a pipeline) or functionality may be highly integrated, depending on the underlying training and inference strategies. A summary of workflows is shown in Figure 2 to facilitate further exploration in this section.

4.1. Underpinning workflows using model integration

Analogies have been made between *generated* speech (output from TTS synthesis) and *manipulated* speech (output from VC synthesis) in the context of evaluating spoofing detection systems [33]. VC synthesis has indeed been described as a form of transformation [37], but the 2016 shift caused by WaveNet pushed TTS towards speaker-adaptive pipelines [65], with VC following in subsequent years [62]. Explicit modelling of speaker identity from embeddings allowed finer control of voice output from neural vocoder conditioning [66]. Encoder-decoder paradigms (Figure 2-a) were applied to TTS [67] and VC [68] in 2017, though these relied on separate vocoders. As WaveNet was losing favour due to training difficulty [69], a key innovation added speaker models to the decoder step [70]. Subsequent work unified decoders with vocoders (Figure 2-b) into a single waveform generator [71].

Legal taxonomies that characterise speech as fully-synthetic versus partially-synthetic, or distinguish generated from manipulated speech, miss techniques wherein synthesis is performed iteratively through refined manipulations, as with diffusion models [72, 73] and flow models [74]. Improvements on the original diffusion techniques now also include explicit modelling of speakers to achieve zero-shot TTS synthesis [75] (Figure 2-b). In addition, voice conversion can functionally be performed with an ASR intermediary, so that the output synthetic voice is entirely reconstructed (via TTS) using speaker identity modelling [76] (Figure 2-c) or with a neural audio codec and large language model (LLM) [77] (Figure 2-d).

Figure 2: Example speech synthesis workflows. (a) modular pipeline [67, 78], (b) end-to-end (GAN, diffusion, flow) [71, 73, 74], (c) ASR-based VC [76], (d) codec-based with LLM [77]. Yellow hatch indicates speaker models.

4.2. Reflections on workflows in AI policy

A recent ‘Guide to Deepfakes for Non-Experts’ claims that the term “synthetic speech” refers to speech generated entirely through AI [13], building upon prior definitions [79]. Further distinctions are made between “fully-synthetic” versus “modified” speech audio. Without careful reading, the guide would appear to conflate *manipulated speech* with the historical objective of modifying voices through timbre transformation as a purely signal processing task. Synthetic speech can be created in many ways, considering the diversity of speaker embedding models (Table 1) and synthesis workflows (Figure 2) now available. A legal dichotomy between generated and manipulated speech risks overlooking nuances that may need to be considered in AI policy transparency obligations for voice deepfakes.

5. Impacts: philosophy and medicine

The disciplines that are now involved with speech synthesis are vast, and a proper analysis of each discipline is out of scope for this paper. This section highlights underpinning issues from philosophy and medicine. In philosophy, debate about the humanness of synthetic speech was conceived in the original Cartesian Test [80] and reappeared centuries later in the Turing Test (Imitation Game) [81]. Recent work contextualises voice cloning in a *post-human framework* [82] where a voice clone can outlive a person after death. The post-human framework is derived partially from the Derridean concept of *hauntology* which suggests that AI-voices occupy a unique spectral space between the present (authentic, aliveness) and the past (simulation, inanimacy). Reviving the identity (or essence of identity) of an individual from their voice as a *digital replica* must now be addressed through policy and regulation [8], and there are profound psychological, social, and cultural implications to consider. In medicine, speech synthesis serves many assistive functions including as a *voice prosthetic* for those who do not have the ability to speak. Voice prosthetics can include brain-computer interfaces [83] and voice reconstruction [84]. A synthetic voice may become more than a communication tool, forming part of a person’s established identity, wherein they may self-identify with their synthetic voice or become known for it [85]. These assistive applications may share the models and workflows discussed in this paper, but would require special treatment in AI policy to ensure that individuals who rely on this technology can participate fully in modern society. Synthetic speech detectors deployed in high-stakes scenarios (e.g., emergency calling hotlines) are *equally worthy* of regulation and policy scrutiny as speech generation capabilities.

6. Conclusion

Bridging vocabulary discussions across disciplines must be approached with caution. Speech scientists are well-placed to inform policymakers of innovation trends and trajectories. Deploying wide-scope terminology into policy is not without risk, especially for high-stakes technologies like speech synthesis. Strong AI policies are ones that are culturally appropriate and also technically sound, so that they may be understood and implemented with the shared goal of preventing harm and promoting safety. This paper has been written with policymakers in mind, in an effort to provide clarity on technical language pertaining to the current state of speech synthesis. After examining what is meant by speech synthesis *models* and *workflows*, policymakers can better assess and revise their legal language to account for current and future capabilities.

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8. Generative AI use disclosure

Generative AI (Anthropic Claude Opus 4.5) was used to search for potential sources, minor editing to improve readability, and assistance with creating LaTeX tables/figures.

9. References

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